

Influence of Broken Home on Academic Performance Among Primary School Pupils in Paikoro Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research work examined the influence of broken home on academic performance among primary school pupils in Paikoro Local Government Area of Niger State. The study employed descriptive survey design. The total of 300 respondents from broken home took part in the study; out of which one hundred (33%) pupils were from death parents, one hundred (33%) pupils from separated parents and one hundred (33%) pupils from divorced parents, from primary six in Paikoro Local Government Area of Niger State. Academic Performance Test score on English Language and Mathematics was used for data collection (APTELM). One hypothesis was tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the analysis indicated that parental separation had no significant differential influence on the academic performance of primary school Boys and Girls ($t=1.332$, $p=0.321$). Similarly, Results of the analysis indicated significant differential influence of parental care on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by either the fathers or the mothers in Paikoro Local Government Area ($t=\text{calculated}$, 2.993, $p=0.003$). Based on this findings, it was recommended that the school authority should intensified efforts to study individual pupil that are enrolled in schools and learn about their family backgrounds so that those that need special attention are identify as soon as possible, in order to design counselling programme that will facilitate their academic activities

Key words: Influence, Broken home, Academic performance, Primary school, Pupils

Introduction

Children acquire initial education and socialization from the parents and other significant persons in the family, Family lays the psychological, moral and spiritual foundation in the overall development of the child. Where and when there is harmony within the family, it translates to a happy home for the child. In happy homes, healthy and peaceful coexistence prevail amongst family members, which in turn breed healthy and happy children. Very often, chances are that some homes are broken that is the members are not live/staying together either as a result of death, separation, divorce or the like. A broken home in this

context, refers to a home that is characterized with single parent, as result of divorce, separation, death of one of the parents.

Hammond (as cited by Alhassan, 2008) discovered that pupils of broken homes exhibit much negative measures such as distractibility, acting out, with time received from others, these go a long way to influence their academic performance in the schools. Alhassan (2008) indicated that a child in the incomplete family is socially and psychologically deprived of a father-figure either to emulate directly or to look for a model of the opposite sex. “In terms of other long-term consequences for children, parental disruption has been shown to be associated with lower socio-economic and academic attainment”. (Yakubu 2010), It can be deduced/inferred that broken homes may affect the development of the children in all aspects of their life. Thus, children of broken homes may be emotionally imbalance and psychologically depressed.

A broken home can also be viewed as to be separated from mother or father, and is like to lose part of the body (Igbinsosa, 2014). Life in a broken home can be stressful for both the child and the parent, and such families are faced with challenges of inadequate financial resource. Schutts (2006) noted that if children from broken homes are to be compared with those from intact homes, it would be seen that the former have more social, academic and emotional problems. Rochlkepart (2003) in Igbinsosa (2014) is of the opinion that the family and its structure play a great role in children’s academic performance. Ayodele (2007) stated that the environment where a child finds himself goes a long way in determining his learning ability and ultimately his academic performance in school.

Broken homes may bring about stress, tension, lack of motivation and frustration obviously these manifestations may act negatively on a Pupil academic performance. Poor academic performance has over the years become rampant, more pronounced and a peculiar feature in the institutions of learning. This has generated a lot of concern among parents, teachers, counselors, educational administrator, as well as in government circle. Broken homes while being a problem of couples are largely a problem of the nation as a whole. Therefore, the influence of broken homes on pupil academic performance is the major concern of this study and the researcher wants to ascertain the influence of broken home on the academic performance of primary school pupils in Paikoro local government area, Niger State.

Statement of the Problem

It is worthy to note that the inhabitants of Paikoro Local Government Area predominantly operate in a polygamous system of marriage. This system has a lot of implications to the stability of some families of many couples in study area. For instance, a man who is not economically viable to maintain one wife but gets married to two or three wives through parental and peer group influence will definitely not be able to cope with the maintenance of the family. And there is a global awareness on the importance of home environment on pupil’s academic performance, the family which is the most important social unit that provides social, psychological and economic security to its members such as children is under threat due to rising cases of broken homes such as divorce, separation, and death of a parent. For this reason, schools are likely to have more pupils whose parents have been divorced, dead or separated than ever before. The rate of broken homes in the present society is becoming alarming as the number of children from broken homes is increasing by the day. The home is meant to be a place filled with joy, happiness with lots of guaranteed security and comfort but it is rather pitiful that the home is neglecting its primary functions thereby causing lots of psychological challenge in the mind of the school pupils.

The emotional and social stress of broken homes may cause hardship, such as inability to resume classes as at when due, inability to purchase necessary learning materials, payment of dues and charges, lack guidance and counselling, monitoring and supervision, security of and freedom from oppression, right of early education, and broken homes due to either separation, death or divorce is one of the factors that may influence pupil academic performance. The presence of a broken home condition may adversely affect pupil’s concentration on their studies and regular attendance in school, it may also lead to exams failures

and also impede academic performance as the pupil is unable to take advantage of learning opportunities at school and at home, for these pupils to be in school with various psychological home conditions will no doubt be in disequilibrium state of mind. It is against this background, the researchers wants to find out the influence of broken homes on academic performances of the pupils (male and female) in public primary schools in paikoro local government area of Niger State.

Objective of the Study

The study sets out to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examined the differential influence of parental separation on academic performance of primary school boys and girls Pupils in Paikoro Local Government Area.
2. To investigate the differential influence of parental care on the academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by either the mother or father in Paikoro Local Government Area

Null Hypotheses

For the purpose of this research work, the following hypotheses were tested;

HO₁ There is no significant differential influence of parental separation on academic performance of primary school boys and girls Pupils in Paikoro Local Government Area.

HO₂ There is no significant differential influence of parental care on the academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by either the mother or the father in Paikoro Local Government Area.

Method

This study adopted Survey research design. Survey research is adopted because the researchers did not manipulate the broken home which is the independent variable of the study or any variables of interest. Survey entails the collection and use of data systematically from a given population to describe certain characteristics features of the population. The population of this study was made up of 690 pupils from broken home, 169 pupils as a result of death, 211 pupils from separated parents and 310 pupils with divorce parents, in 11 selected primary schools in Paikoro Local Government Area of Niger State, which comprises of 11 wards. Based on respondents responses to different stratify variables in the demographic items questions of the instrument used.

The sample size for this study was made up of 300 pupils. Simple random sampling technique was used to select one school each from the 11 wards that constitute Paikoro Local Government Area out of total number of 115 primary schools in the research area of Niger State. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample for this study based on the variation in the population of each school with parental death at 100, parental separation 100 and parental divorce 100 pupils respectively. This was based on recommendation of Aderemo (2012), that for research work in education, a sample size of between 20% may be sufficient to use.

The instrument titled “Academic Performance test on English Language and Mathematics, developed by the researchers in collaboration with the English Language and Mathematics Teachers based on their curriculum was used for data collection for the study. The instrument is made up of three sections A, B and C. Section A contain 4 items on the Bio Data of the respondents to indicate pupils from broken home as a result of parental death, parental separation and parental divorce, section B and C contains 25 items each for Academic Performance Test on English Language and Mathematics respectively. The English Language and Mathematics test were scored two (2) marks for each correct test item totaling 100 marks, while “0” was awarded for each wrong test item. The instrument was rated this 100-50 = Good Academic Performance while 49-0 = Low Academic Performance. The instrument was validated by three Lecturers in department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The observations of tenses, grammar, suggestions and recommendation of these lecturers were effected to gain the face validity of the instrument. Test re-test reliability method was used by administer 20 copies of instrument to pupils in Paggo primary school twice within the interval of two weeks. The result of the two test scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correction Co-efficient (PPMC) statistical tool.

The instrument yields internal consistence of r value .82 and .76 for English Language and Mathematics sections respectively. The reliability coefficient was considered adequate for the internal consistencies of the instrument.

The researchers were assisted by the teachers as research assistants to administer the instrument to the sample respondents from selected schools. Two weeks were used for administration of the instrument. Fifty (50) minutes each were given to the respondents to answer questions on academic performance test for English Language and Mathematics. The instrument was administered to 300 male and female respondents. When the respondents finished answering the academic performance test, the researchers collected the answered academic performance tests with the help of two (2) school staff/teachers. The data collected from the respondents were subjected to statistical analysis. Inferential statistics of t-test was used to test the hypothesis. Decision on outcome of hypotheses testing was based on 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: t-Test on differential influence of parental Separation on Academic Performance of Boys and Girls primary school pupils

Variables	No	Df	Mean	STD	t _{cal}	(P)
Boys	50		48.3320	20.6402		
					1.332 ^{ns}	0.321
Girls	50	49	46.2200	22.5412		

NS = Not Significant at 0.05Level of significance (2tailed)

Table1 show the t-test comparison of Mean scores of Boys and Girls of primary school Pupils with parental separation background. From the table, there is no significant differential influence between the mean scores of male pupils (48.3320) and that of the female pupils (46.2200). Because the calculated p value of 0.321 is greater than 0.05 alpha level of significance at t-test value 1.332 and df of forty-nine. This shows that parental separation have no significant differential influence on the academic performance of primary school Boys and Girls in the study area. Hence, the null Hypothesis which states that there is no significant differential influence of parental separation on academic performance of primary school boys and girls Pupils is here accepted.

Table 2: t-test on differential influence of parental care on Academic Performance of Pupils brought up by Fathers and Mothers

Variables	No	df	Mean	STD	t _{cal}	(p)
Pupils with Fathers	150		44.5867	21.8495		
		149			2.993*	0.003
Pupils with Mothers	150		50.000	22.3036		

*Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table2: above revealed significant differential influence of parental care on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by father or mother in the study area. This is because the calculated p value of 0.003 is less than the 0.05alpha level of significance at a t-calculated value of 2.993 and df of one hundred and forty-nine (149). This shows that parental care have a significant differential influence on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by father or mother. Hence, the null hypothesis

which states that there is no significant differential influence of parental care on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by father or mother in the study area is rejected.

Discussion

The study revealed that there is no significant differential influence of parental separation on academic performance of primary school boys and girl in Paikoro Local Government Area of Niger State. The result concurred with the view of Frank (2012) that children of separation parents had poor concentration in the school and this had negative influence on pupils academic performance regardless of gender, the findings also concurs with study done by Kapambwe (2014) who found that pupil from broken home have emotional problem which in turn lead to poor academic performance in school because they are unable to turn their energies and attention in the direction of learning, such children are dominated by more urgent unfulfilled psychological and emotional needs. Because of these unfulfilled psychological and emotional needs, learning becomes less urgent and irrelevant. The children, instead of concentrating on school work, direct their attention on how they would satisfy their urgent needs.

Children need Love, affection and motivation and these ingredients seem to be lacking in children from broken homes for both sexes. Olatunde and Tunde in Yakubu (2010) confirmed that parental separation had significant influence on pupils` academic performance since the pupils lacked necessary psychological and financial support to enhance their learning ability but on the bases of gender is the same. Douglas (2011) stated that in most broken homes, the children are generally disadvantaged because they are usually deprived academically, economically, socially and culturally, pupils from broken homes always have a deficit. As a result of loss of parent, these pupils of both sexes suffer psychological problems. This finding also agree with other researchers like Bichlery (2001), Olatunde and Abisola (2010) in Yakubu (2010), who found that pupils from single-parenting homes exhibit lower self- esteem, lower achievement motivation, lower tolerance for delay of gratification and lower academic achievement than those from intact homes where both father and mother are present. The explanation for poor academic achievement of adolescents from broken homes is that single-parent or guardian has so much work and family responsibilities that require time, attention, and money which he/she cannot meet with the consequence of paying less attention to the education of his/her children. The resultant effect therefore, is poor academic achievement on the part of the children from broken or single-parent homes.

Results of study also revealed significant differential influence of parental care on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by father and mother ($t = 2.993$ and p value 0.003) among primary school pupils investigated. This implies that parental care has significant differential influence on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by father or mother. In comparing the influence parental care between those pupils taken care by father and mother, the results suggest that the influence of these care given to pupils are not proportional. The finding agrees with Douglas (2011), who observed that for many young children, it is the early contacts with their mothers that are likely to have the greatest influence on learning and also later ages too, it is the mother who is more concerned than the father with school problems. Douglas (2011) also observed that mothers are always with their children so as to assist them with school problems. The finding disagrees with (Frank, 2012) which stated that loving and caring parents regardless who taken custody of child is significant to the child academic performance and vice-versa. Analyzing such a situation, the researcher thought it was possible to ascertain that such homes could not offer that love and care which is provided by two biological parents to his or her children. Research results have proved that there is a close correlation between the meaning of education of parent and students learning achievement. Salihu (2008) described broken home as a great evil, it is ever more painful than death many things are thrown out of gear in the event of divorce between the man and wife, society and man will have a bad record hanging on his neck, where there are children situation becomes more bad especially their education.

The pupil whose memories are associated with resentment cannot be expected to compete successfully with those whose memories are associated with a feeling of what we call personal satisfaction or a sense of achievement. Pupil's academic performances from broken families is affected by home-based factors. Pupils from broken families often become truants at schools. Aremu (2000) stresses that academic failure is not only frustrating to the students and the parents, its effects are equally grave on the society in terms of dearth of manpower in all spheres of the economy and politics. Ononuga (2005) asserted that education of the parents has an impact on the level of the performances of the pupils.

Peter (2005) states that pupils thrive best when they are brought up in a stable family in which two parents are able to give them a great deal of care and attention, encouraging them, on one hand, to develop their own life and interest and providing them on the other, with secure base to which they can return and in which they can always find comfort and support.

Ministry of Education (2007) states that the learning ability of a pupil affected by home background is likely to be impaired. It has been noted that without any instruction from a parent, a child given only the requisite nourishment would survive into adulthood. This is because the body is well equipped to protect the child from environment harm. However such a child through grow would remain uncivilized, a veritable danger to himself and his environment and community, parental instruction is vital for the right outcome to emanate from a child. (The post, 2011)

Dowd (as cited by Igbinosa, 2014), says; in most broken homes (parental separation) the pupils are generally regarded as being deprived academically, economically, socially and culturally. Their environments are not conducive to learning and in which education is not adequate. Pupils from broken home families always have deficit. As a result of loss of one parent these children suffer, psychological problems. Father-son or Mother-son contact is an essential element in moral development, without it, moral bankruptcy arises.

Ballantine and Hammerick (2011) observed that children from broken households have lower grades, lower test scores and higher drop up rates on average than those from two-parent households. These results are also influence by factors such as the education level of parent and the level involvement by the absence of a parent. Pupils form broken families are likely to receive less parental encouragement and attention with respect to educational activities than pupils who live with both biological parents. Pupils from broken families often have lower educational expectations, less monitoring of school work and less supervision than pupils from intact families (Astone &McLanahan in Kapambwe, 2014).

Wiseman, (2011) says that losing parent support either temporarily or permanently is extremely stressing for a child. Many studies have documented an association between marital disruption and a wide range of deleterious effects in children. These include: poor performance in school, emotional stress, insecurity and anxiety as factors which effectively affect the Children Schools progress Fraser (2010). Kapambwe (as cited by Igbinosa, 2014) states that pupils with emotional problems do poorly in school because they are unable to turn their energies and attention in the direction of learning such children are dominated by more urgent unfulfilled psychological and emotional needs.

Mchanahan and sanderfur (as cited by Kasonde, 2002) give an extensive description of the three types of resources (i.e. financial, parental, and social) that are important in explaining the impact of living with a single parent on children changes of future success. First of all, they underline the importance of financial resources and the loss of income that generally goes together with family disruption. In short, this is due to the fact that after divorce two households need to be supported instead of only one and thus a lot of household expense cannot be shared any longer, which is also called a loss of economies of scale. The most direct effect of this loss of income on educational/academic achievement of children is the fact that the quality of the school they attend generally is lower. The higher the income of parents the more possibilities they have to live in neighborhoods with good public schools or to send their children to a school of their preference. Income can also affect school outcomes through enabling a child to participate in extracurricular activities like lesson after schools, special trips or summer camps. Such activities improve

pupil skills directly, but also indirectly via generally intellectual stimulation, which impact positively on subsequence learning.

In addition to a loss of financial resources, a loss parental involvement is generally associated with a divorce or separation, parental involvement is supposed to positively impact on pupils' academic achievement (Park, Byun & Kim, 2011). It mainly comprehends the time parents spend with their children on reading, helping with the home work or by listening to the stories about their experience at schools, as well as the ability and willingness of parent to monitor and supervise children social activities outside school, which reduce their opportunity to get in trouble. In addition, it refers to activities in relation to schools such as volunteering at school events, attending a parent teacher organization, or contacting teachers and school officials (Park, Byun & kim, 2011). After a divorce or separation the quality and quantity of parental involvement decreases. For instance people are likely to experiences high levels of stress and anxiety after the disruption. Also broken homes parents have to divide their time between work and home, and consequently can devote less time to their children compared to a situation in which two parents run a household. Moreover, they are not controlled and corrected in "parenting" by the other parent, which makes it less sure whether one is behaving in appreciate ways.

Apart from the direct effect of the decreases quality and quantity of parental involvement on children's academic performance, simply because of the reduced educational support they receive, the divorce itself and the reduction of parental involvements afterward will cause emotional and other related problems (problems of concentration for the children involved and hence indirectly lead to poor academic achievement among pupils from broken homes compared to pupils form two-parent families. Mclanahan and Sandefur (as cited by Kasonde 2007), after the divorce or separation, single parents may not had the time or energy to keep investing in personal relationships, because of stress, or depression and consequently, loss friends without making new ones (immediately). Especially regarding former mutual friends, it may be difficult for both partners to maintain these relationships.

Furthermore, it is likely that community ties weaken after a divorce or separation, due to a possible move to another neighborhoods or town. This includes a reduction of social capital as emotional support and information about the broader community, over all, the social network of divorce parents, will thus decrease which implies that, for instance they have less information about which teacher are good and which are not, and they will be less familiar with extracurricular activities. These might negatively impact on pupils/children's academic performance.

To sum up, the relevant and available literatures reviewed showed that broken home contributed to poor pupil academic performance in school and in most cases. Study such as Frank (2012), noted that pupils from broken home experience a lot of emotional difficulties as they try to cope with changes brought about by their parents' death, separation and divorce. However it was noted that not all the children from broken homes performed poorly in class. The study also shows the home environment was critical in academic performance of pupils, as learning whether at home, or school occurred through environment. Home environment as a factor is vital as it exert considerable influence on pupil performance. The home and the school are complementary as much of what is done in the classroom may be undone during the time the pupils are away from school.

Conclusion

The parental separation had no differential influence on academic performance of primary school boys and girls pupils of Paikoro Local Government Area. Parental care had differential influence on academic performance of primary school pupils brought up by Father and Mother only home.

Recommendations

Counsellors, School Psychologists, Teachers and school authorities should pay attention to set of pupils from separated parental background through proper counselling and other supporting services, in order to make them focused on their academic activities. The school authority should intensified efforts to study individual pupil that is enrolled in schools and learned about his/her family backgrounds so that those

that need special attention are identify as soon as possible, in order to design counselling programmed that will facilitate their academic activities.

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